

OXIDATIVE DEAMINATION OF THE AMINO-ACIDS.

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The oxidation of the amino-acids by potato-tyrosinase was first observed by Chodat and Schweizer (*Arch. Sci. Phys. Nat.*, 1913, 35, 140). The products of reaction were ammonia, carbon dioxide and an aldehyde containing one carbon atom less than the original amino-acid. The rate of the above reaction was found to be much increased in the presence of certain phenols such as *p*-cresol and catechol. They explained this deamination by the direct action of tyrosinase on amino-acids and the phenols caused acceleration by combining with the reaction products (Schweizer, *Biochem. Z.*, 1917, 78, 37). When phenols were not present, the uncertainty in the detection of ammonia and aldehyde was explained to be due to their further reaction among themselves.

On repetition of the above experiments of Chodat and Schweizer, Happold and Raper (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 92) showed that the deamination of the amino-acids is not due to the direct action of tyrosinase but due to the formation of *o*-quinones from phenol. They investigated the effect of the addition of *p*-cresol, phenol, catechol, resorcinol, quinol and *p*-benzoquinone on the system tyrosinase—amino-acid. From the experimental results they found that only those phenols which are likely to give *o*-quinone or a derivative of it, caused deamination. They studied the action of *o*-quinone prepared by the method of Willstätter and Muller (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 2580) under identical conditions in which the experiments were carried out in the absence of tyrosinase and found that this substance attacked the amino-acids with the production of ammonia.

Pugh and Raper (*Biochem. J.*, 1927, 21, 1370) similarly showed that the deamination of glycine could be effected by adding *o*-homoquinone in place of *o*-benzoquinone. They showed the formation of *o*-quinones by the action of tyrosinase on catechol and certain other phenols by actual isolation.

Robinson and McCance (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 251) working simultaneously over the same point came to the same conclusion as Happold and Raper (*loc. cit.*). But as regards the mechanism of the reaction they did not accept the view that *o*-quinone brought about the secondary oxidation of the amino-acids; for they observed that both the diminution of the amino-nitrogen and the production of ammonia occurred in the case of glycine

and resorcinol in presence of tyrosinase from *basidiomycete Lactarius vellereus*. From these facts they opined that the system tyrosinase—phenol—amino-acid was a much more complicated one than Happold and Raper thought. According to them the amino-acids played an active part in the system and that no *ortho*-quinone was probably formed.

Kisch and Schuwirth (*Biochem. Z.*, 1931, 252, 1; 1932, 244, 440; 1932, 247, 371 *et al*) have studied the oxidative deamination of the amino-acids by the catalytic activity of *o*-quinone and some other substances producing *p*-quinone. They have shown that *o*-quinone is highly specific in its action. Quinol, benzoquinone, protocatechuic acid, pyrogallol, phloroglucinol are unable to effect deamination at p_H 6.8 and cause a feeble deamination at p_H 9.12 (*Biochem. Z.*, 1932, 259, 63). At p_H 9.12 resorcinol is highly active producing 50% of the calculated ammonia from glycine. From the above facts it is evident that the exact mechanism of the deamination of the amino-acids in the system tyrosinase—phenol—amino-acid is yet a disputable point.

Now the mode of action of tyrosinase on phenols can be imitated by sols of tungstic acid and molybdic acid in presence of hydrogen peroxide as shown by the present author in a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 291). As the system tyrosinase—phenol can bring about the secondary oxidation of the amino-acids, it is expected that the system phenol—sol— H_2O_2 will bring about the same oxidation and it has actually been found to be the case. An attempt is therefore made to throw light on the mechanism of the reaction and the part played by the amino-acids.

In this paper the author has made a systematic study of the influence of a wide range of substances on the secondary oxidation of the amino-acids by means of hydrogen peroxide in presence of tungstic acid sol. The substances used are phenol, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-cresols, catechol, resorcinol, quinol, pyrogallol, guaiacol, carvacrol, thymol, phloroglucinol, α - and β -naphthols, thioglycollic acid, tyrosine and gallic acid. The amino-acids used are glycine, alanine, leucine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid and tyrosine. In addition to these, the action of the following quinones, *o*- and *p*-quinones, α -naphthoquinone, *p*-xyloquinone, phenanthraquinone and acenaphthinequinone, on amino-acids without the addition of catalyst and H_2O_2 , is also studied.

EXPERIMENTAL.

All the substances taken were chemically pure. Conductivity water was used in the preparation of all aqueous solutions. Either Na_2WO_4 , as

it is, or tungstic acid sol was used as catalyst. The sol was prepared by the addition of dilute HCl to sodium tungstate by the usual method and its p_H was about 5. Fresh solution of hydrogen peroxide was prepared from Merck's perhydrol. Amino-acids (Pfansteihl) were dissolved in phosphate buffer of p_H 6.5. The experiments were carried out in Pyrex conical flasks kept at room temperature about 25°. Preliminary experiments showed that no oxidation of the amino-acids occurs in the system amino-acid—sol— H_2O_2 . Neither any ammonia nor any aldehyde could be detected even after 72 hours. But when a phenol was added to the above system, oxidation of the amino-acid took place. The reaction in the case of glycine may be represented as

The formation of formaldehyde can be easily detected by means of Schryver's reagent, starting with suitable concentration (0.5 g.) of glycine in presence of *p*-cresol.

The reaction mixture consisting of phenol—catalyst— H_2O_2 —amino-acid was allowed to stand at room temperature for a period of 24 hours. After that period the total quantity of ammonia in the whole of the reaction mixture was estimated by the method of White-horn as described in the oxidation of tyrosine. The amount of ammonia liberated is indicated by varying number of + ive signs. A negative sign indicates the complete absence of ammonia, + sign signifies "Ammonia easily detectable." The results are given in Table I. Strict control was kept for every experiment in which water was added in place of the solution of phenol.

TABLE I.

$H_2O_2 = 45$ mg. $Na_2WO_4 = 0.002M$. Total volume = 25 c. c.
Glycine = 50 mg.

Phenols used.	Deamination.	Phenols used-	Deamination.
Phenol (20 mg.)	+ +	Carvacrol (100 mg.) dissolved in minimum quantity of alcohol	+ +
<i>o</i> -Cresol (20 mg.)	+ +	Thymol (100 mg.) dissolved in minimum quantity of alcohol	+ +
<i>m</i> -Cresol (20 mg.)	+ +	α -Naphthol (100 mg.) dissolved in alcohol	+ + +
<i>p</i> -Cresol (20 mg.)	+ + +	β -Naphthol, saturated solution in H_2O (10 c.c.)	+ + +
Catechol (50 mg.)	+ + +	Gallic acid (100 mg.) in minimum quantity of alcohol.	+ +
Quinol (50 mg.)	+ +	Thioglycollic acid (100 mg.)	- ve
Resorcinol (50 mg.)	+		
Pyrogallol (50 mg.)	+ + +		
Phloroglucinol (100 mg.)	-ve		
Guaiaacol (50 mg.)	+ +		
Tyrosine in HCl brought to a p_H about 4 with pure NaOH— (50 mg.)	-ve		

TABLE I (contd.).

Phenols used.	Deamination.	Phenols used.	Deamination.
Alanine = 60 mg.			
<i>p</i> -Cresol (80 mg.)	+ +	Quinol (100 mg.)	+
Catechol (100 mg.)	+	Resorcinol (100 mg.)	?
Leucine = 70 mg.			
<i>p</i> -Cresol (80 mg.)	+ +	Quinol (100 mg.)	+
Catechol (100 mg.)	+	Resorcinol (100 mg.)	?
Aspartic acid, saturated solution in phosphate buffer of pH 6.5 = 10 c.c.			
<i>p</i> -Cresol (80 mg.)	+ +	Quinol (100 mg.)	+
Catechol (100 mg.)	+ +	Resorcinol (100 mg.)	Traces.
Glutamic acid-saturated solution in phosphate buffer of pH 6.5 = 10 c.c.			
<i>p</i> -Cresol (80 mg.)	+ + +	Quinol (100 mg.)	+ +
Catechol (100 mg.)	+ +	Resorcinol (100 mg.)	+
Tyrosine dissolved in HCl adjusted to a pH about 4. = 100mg.			
<i>p</i> -Cresol (100 mg.)	+		

In Table II is given the action of various quinones on amino-acids in the absence of the sol and H_2O_2 . The total quantity of ammonia liberated was estimated after 24 hours by the usual method.

TABLE II.

Quinones.	Glycine = 50 mg.	Deamination.
Quinone prepared by the method of Willstätter and Muller.		
<i>p</i> -Quinone sat. soln. in H_2O (10 c.c.)		+ + +
<i>p</i> -Xyloquinone sat. soln. in alcohol (10 c.c.)		+ + +
α -Naphthoquinone sat. solution in alcohol (10 c.c.)		+ +
Phenanthraquinone sat. soln. in H_2O (10 c. c.)		+ +
Acenaphthine-quinone sat. soln. in alcohol (10 c.c.)		+ + +
Alanine, sat. soln. in phosphate buffer of pH 6.3 = 10 c.c.		
<i>o</i> -Quinone		+ + +
<i>p</i> -Quinone		+ +
Leucine, sat. soln. in phosphate buffer of pH 6.3 = 10 c.c.		
<i>o</i> -Quinone		+ + +
<i>p</i> -Quinone		+ +

The following quantitative experiments were carried out by determining the amino-nitrogen content of the system by means of the macro-form of Van Slyke's apparatus. The amino-nitrogen was determined in a small sample (8 c.c.), at the beginning and after 24 hours. Strict control was kept for every experiment in which the amino-acid was replaced by buffer and necessary correction was made to the initial and final volumes of amino-nitrogen obtained. No diminution of $\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$ takes place in the system amino-acid—sol— H_2O_2 even after 72 hours. The results are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

$\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 = 120$ mg. Na-tungstate = $0.002M$. Temp. = 25° . Total vol. = 40 c.c.

Phenols used.	Amino acids.	$\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$		Loss of $\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$.
		0 hr.	24 hrs.	
<i>p</i> -cresol (0.196 g.)	Glycine	9.439 mg.	8.368 mg.	1.071 mg.
	Alanine	9.384	9.009	0.375
	Leucine	9.494	8.611	0.883
Catechol (0.2 g.)	Glycine	9.494	8.584	0.91
	Alanine	8.592	8.270	0.322
	Leucine	7.979	7.229	0.75
Resorcinol (0.2 g.)	Glycine	9.231	8.998	0.233
	Alanine	8.552	8.645	—
	Leucine	7.818	7.925	—
Quinol (0.2 g.)	Glycine	9.439	8.742	0.697
	Alanine	9.022	8.807	0.215
	Leucine	7.979	7.444	0.535
<i>p</i> -Quinone (sat. soln. in $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 10$ c.c.)	Glycine	9.558	8.116	1.442
	Alanine	9.314	8.285	1.029
	Leucine	8.989	7.743	1.246

Of the amino-acids, glycine, alanine and leucine, glycine is more readily deaminised than leucine and leucine is more easily deaminised than alanine. The same observation was also made by Robinson and McCance (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 251). Of the phenols, *p*-cresol, catechol, quinol, and resorcinol, *p*-cresol is most active, then come catechol, quinol and lastly resorcinol.

From the above tables it is evident that the oxidative deamination of the amino-acids in the secondary system takes place in the presence of all phenols in the primary system,

The following experiments were carried out to show whether the phenols act as catalytic agents in the deamination of the amino-acids by hydrogen peroxide in the absence of the sol. The diminution of the $\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$ content of the system amino-acid—phenol— H_2O_2 was measured after 24 hours by keeping proper control. The results are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

$\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 = 120 \text{ mg.}$ Temp. = 30° . Total volume = 40 c.c.

Phenols used.	Amino-acids.	$\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$ in 8 c.c.		Loss of $\text{NH}_2\text{-N}$.
		0 hr.	24 hrs.	
<i>p</i> -Cresol (0.196 g.)	Glycine	9.692 mg.	9.692 mg.	—
	Alanine	9.326	9.299	—
	Leucine	9.291	9.238	—
Catechol (0.2 g.)	Glycine	9.318	9.210	0.108 mg.
	Alanine	9.049	8.996	—
	Leucine	9.127	9.154	—
Resorcinol (0.2 g.)	Glycine	9.9603	9.4248	0.5355
	Alanine	9.426	9.533	—
	Leucine	9.529	9.689	—
Quinol (0.2 g.)	Glycine	9.5854	9.4248	0.1606
	Alanine	9.132	9.132	—
	Leucine	9.439	9.385	—

DISCUSSION.

On the basis of the experimental results in the oxidation of the amino-acids by the system phenol—tungstic acid— H_2O_2 , the deamination of the amino-acids can be explained by the following mechanism of reaction.

The deamination of the amino-acids does not occur by sol and hydrogen peroxide but when a phenol is added, oxidation takes place. As phenols are all oxidised by sol and H_2O_2 , so phenol itself or some oxidation product of phenol is responsible for the deamination, or the oxidation of the amino-acids is an induced reaction by the primary system phenol—sol— H_2O_2 . It has been observed that though *p*-cresol is most active in causing deamination of the amino-acids in the secondary system, it does not catalyse the oxidation of amino-acids by means of hydrogen peroxide. In the case of catechol and quinol slight amount of ammonia is produced only with glycine (*vide*, Table IV). This slight deamination is probably due to the formation

of the corresponding quinones by means of hydrogen peroxide, while its absence with *p*-cresol is due to the fact that it is not attacked by hydrogen peroxide alone. The facts with resorcinol are somewhat different. A greater amount of deamination of glycine occurs by means of hydrogen peroxide in presence of resorcinol alone than it does by the system resorcinol—sol— H_2O_2 (*vide*, Tables III and IV). So it is obvious that in the deamination of glycine by hydrogen peroxide, resorcinol itself acts catalytically. Should the deamination be due to some oxidation product of resorcinol, the amount of deamination would be reverse to that actually observed.

Now in Table I, we have used a great number of phenolic substances which are likely to produce different quinones and have found that they all cause the deamination of amino-acids. Tyrosine is, however, peculiar in this respect. It is neither deaminised itself during the first few stages of oxidation, as shown in the previous paper, nor cause any external deamination of amino-acids. The mechanism of the oxidation of tyrosine by tyrosinase has been extensively studied by Raper and his school and the absence of deamination has been explained (*cf.* Kar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 271). Tyrosine is deaminised slightly by the system *p*-cresol—sol— H_2O_2 , when it is used as an external amino-acid. Schweizer (*Biochem. Z.*, 1917, 76, 37) also could detect small quantities of ammonia with Nessler's reagent after tyrosine had been acted upon by tyrosinase in presence of *p*-cresol.

In Table II, the action of different quinones on amino-acids are studied and it has been found that they all cause deamination in the absence of sol and hydrogen peroxide.

If the oxidation of the amino-acids be an induced reaction by the primary system, phenol-sol- H_2O_2 , the systems tyrosine-sol- H_2O_2 , and thioglycollic acid-sol- H_2O_2 , would also cause deamination. With both the systems no trace of ammonia could be detected.

From the above facts we can draw the conclusion that the deamination of the amino-acids is not due to the formation of *ortho*-quinone alone in the primary system but due to the formation of all quinones. The amino-acids do not play any active part as Robinson and McCance supposed (*loc. cit.*).

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